

Nuclear Acceleration Strategies (NAS) for Climate Change Mitigation

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I. INTRODUCTION

The biggest challenges in Climate Change are the production of electricity, economic development worldwide, and reduction of Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions. By combining these three challenges, there is a need to consider which technology can help solve the problem.

The country's energy matrix distribution depends on its natural resources and the energy policies that the government wants to apply based on the demand for electricity that it is needed to cover. Since several decades ago, the nuclear source has been demonstrated to be reliable, safe, and low carbon energy to produce power.

Through the implementation of Nuclear Acceleration Strategies (NSA) of early recruitment in Human Resources Development, International Cooperation promotion for young talents, the consolidation of an International Regulation for Generation IV (GEN IV) technology, and a methodology for Nuclear Power Expansion for GEN IV will create awareness and improve the good practices in the nuclear industry to reach the decarbonization goal.

II. BACKGROUND

Electricity production around the world has been increasing rapidly with population growth. Different sources like coal, wind, solar, hydro, geothermal, and nuclear are part of the energy matrix distribution to cover the electricity demand. The energy policy of a country depends on energy sources. According to the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), by 2050, all the countries worldwide should generate electricity through low carbon sources. The nuclear source helps to meet the growing demand for a clean and low-carbon mix that is dependable[1].

Nuclear power has been a capable source of energy for decades. Its capacity provides a considerable demand for electricity generation and maintains baseload power 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, 365 days a year[2]. Nuclear technology is one of the most optimal solutions to reduce CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere[3,4].

Nuclear energy now generates 10% of the world's electricity, attributable to 443 nuclear power reactors. Nuclear has shown that it's the second-largest source of low-carbon power, and 32 countries generate their power based on nuclear, covering a total demand for electricity of 393 241 MWe[5,6].

III. STRATEGIES

A. Early Recruitment

More than deploying the technology to decarbonize the planet, it is required the development of human power. Accelerating more personnel training to focus on the energy industry and educating more professionals about current and future demands will help to understand the problem globally. If the Nuclear Sector concentrates on recruiting people earlier and speeding up their preparation for their professional careers, in parallel showing the benefits to politicians of energy transition and demonstrating the facts through the example of other member states that welcome nuclear energy in their land will create a conscious strategy[7].

When more educational institutions point out the importance of nuclear culture, the government authorities will start looking at all the benefits of the technology. Showing the advantages of nuclear technology in terms of economic development [8]. National Liaison Officers (NLOs) need to engage more in promoting nuclear energy at different educational levels in each respective member state. Creating flexibility in the infrastructure systems for young raising talents in the countries will attract more students to develop a career in the nuclear field[9].

B. International Cooperation for Young Talents

Another aspect that it is essential to consider is to keep embracing the international cooperation relationships, attracting more talents to a particular nuclear program to develop the infrastructure faster. For example, if more international experts work for a couple of years in the regulation system, each country could establish the International Regulatory Body instead of a National Regulatory Body to deploy Generation IV technology[10,11]. Some critical areas to

keep active international cooperation are Radiation Protection, Work Management, Chemistry, Non-Proliferation, Emergency Preparedness, International Nuclear Law, Engineering, and Operations and Maintenance.

Creating a solid bridge of cooperation will help in the race against climate change to deploy advanced technology. There are four key areas to identify in the existing nuclear program infrastructure:

- 1) Active communication, which brings an open dialogue to identify the needs in each member state
- 2) Signing Memorandum of Understandings (MOUs) will activate potential partnerships between several organizations
- 3) Exchange Technology will create a vision between the current and future participants to transfer knowledge and good practices.
- 4) Commercializing and deploying a particular technology in a member state based on the previous areas will help achieve an advanced nuclear program infrastructure.

A global synergy and balance will develop the consistency for accelerating human resources development and mitigating climate change through optimization and continuous iteration process between all the stakeholders involved.

C. 4 Harmony Program

To stimulate the development of Gen IV reactors, the 4 Harmony Program was suggested in 2019, and worldwide collaboration is required to unify the essential features of Gen IV design and simplify the certification process. The plan for Harmony is based on attaining the goal of harmonization with other international working groups to improve collaboration [12].

Countless potential initiatives and projects for Gen IV reactors were anticipated; the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) drove the International Program Innovative Nuclear Reactors Fuel Cycles (INPRO) program[13,14,15] and the Generic Reactor Safety Review (GRSR) service; the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development/Nuclear Energy Agency (OECD/NEA)[16,17] headed the Multinational Design Evaluation Program (MDEP)[18]; the World Nuclear Association (WNA) proceeded to run the Cooperation in Reactor Design Evaluation and Licensing (CORDEL)[19]. The Generation IV Information Organization (GIF) is an international forum that gathers information regarding Generation IV reactors. Different groups speak in various methodical languages, but they aim to advance Gen-IV technology. As a result, a harmonization program would be a good alternative for bringing together existing Gen-IV technology organizations for current development and deployment activities. The primary framework of the 4 Harmony project, which consists of four levels.

The first level involves the Academic Training, which includes neutronics, thermal hydraulics, materials, construction, and operation, is the first level. It will take additional human resources with a comprehensive understanding of Gen IV technology's expertise and development. The Summer Institute of the World Nuclear University may be an excellent venue for gathering and disseminating information. The industrial consultant is the second level. An International Cooperation Convention between various consultants should be developed to aim and support the design and regulation. The third level is an international committee comprised of the IAEA, NEA, WNA, and GIF, collaborating to assess the new design's constraints. Consequently, a new design that differs from the previous six designs has the potential to gain international attention. Furthermore, this project has the potential to grow.

The long-term aim is for a single worldwide Gen-IV cooperation agency to emerge from implementing a standard guideline for design technology based on consensus and shared values. Figure 1 illustrates a flow chart for developing an International Collaboration plan, including the intersection and global collaboration between organizations. This concept might be used to determine the availability and capabilities of technology at the industry level after selecting the evaluation assessment. Harmonization with global standards is an essential aspect of GIF evolution; if pursued, it might provide a pathway for international standardization and regulation, which would be a substantial advantage. The INPRO project will assess the competence and long-term viability of the design proposal's fuel cycle process, using GIF criteria as well. Following that, it will send the results to MDEP. MDEP might be an approach for recommending worldwide recommendations that include overall design and safety requirements[20]. MDEP might play a role in this process as a system controller by developing novel techniques to assess national regulatory agencies' resources and knowledge considering new reactor designs[21]. Finally, the final data might assist in submitting documents to the National Regulatory Authority for License and the commercialization of reactor models.

D. Nuclear Power Expansion Strategy

During the economic crisis, it is fundamental to review and analyze which reliable sources of electricity and energy have helped tackle the pandemic challenges and how nuclear technology supports other medicine, food, and agriculture applications. As electricity demand continues growing, greenhouse gas emissions must decrease to mitigate climate change, and there must be a transition to cleaner sources to reduce air pollution. The transition involves more technology with low-carbon energy sources, and nuclear plays an essential role in this aspect.

Figure 1: International Development Process

IV. METHODOLOGY

A practical methodology is needed to allocate strategic Nuclear Power Expansion (NPE) in a particular member state. Depending on which Generation IV reactor technology is intended to be deployed[22]. Figure 2 contains a suggested strategy that could be implemented for a NPE Strategy.

This study focuses on the proposal of NPE in China to reduce CO₂ emissions and install power operations for a long-term process assessment. Comparative studies and data are listed to describe the benefits of nuclear technology to consider as a scenario for diversifying the energy portfolio in China and propose a method for reactor technology selection. Simulations were carried out in Super Decisions Software implementing Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Analytical Network Process (ANP) to find which reactor technology is more optimal to apply for the proposal of NPE. Nuclear hybrid energy systems combine several energy sources to reduce CO₂ emissions and produce clean energy to meet the SDGs.

Figure 2: Nuclear Power Expansion Process.

V. RESULTS

The sensitivity analyses combine several criteria to represent energy sources to reduce CO₂ emissions and produce clean energy to meet SDGs; the results are shown in figure 1. (2). The criteria listed in this case are 1) Reduction of CO₂ emissions, 2) Supply a constant amount of electricity, 3) Affordable energy (SDG7), and 4) Flexibility in base load power. The Network Implementation model that connects the several criteria, reactors technology alternatives with the design specifications. Finally, figure 3 provides the sensitivity study for AHP and ANP analyses helping in decision-making.

Figure 3: Sensitivity Analyses

VI. CONCLUSION

Availability of sufficient, secure, and renewable energy is essential to achieving SDGs by mitigating hunger through health and education advances, encouraging economic growth, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Nuclear power, like other technology, delivers electricity to ultimately achieve a high quality of life, nutritional health, a safe atmosphere, and a prosperous economy. In addition, nuclear technology, enhanced sewage facilities, well-functioning health care, education facilities, and efficient transport and telecommunications can provide stable electricity by finding strategies that accelerate the advanced technology development the global decarbonization goal by 2050 could be achieved.

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